

Nonprofit Business Model Canvas

MISSION STATEMENT

KEY PARTNERS

Who are our Key Partners and Key Suppliers?
Which Key Resources are we acquiring from partners?
Which Key Activities do our partners perform?
Who will fund us?

Example Partnerships

- Strategic alliances between non-competitors
- Joint ventures to create new "X"
- Cause Marketing Alliances
- Advocacy Alliances
- Buyer-Supplier relationships to assure reliable supplies
- Low-end donors
- High-end donors
- Philanthropists

KEY ACTIVITIES

Which Key Activities do our Social Value Propositions require?
What activities are needed to sustain operations?

Categories

- Marketing
- Campaigns
- Events
- Production
- Development
- Training
- Networking
- Research
- Service Delivery

KEY RESOURCES

What Key Resources do our Social Value Propositions Require?
What other Key Resources are needed at the engagement level and the operations level?

Examples

- Physical
- Intellectual (brand patents, copyrights, data)
- Human
- Financial

OPERATIONS

ENGAGEMENT

SOCIAL VALUE PROPOSITION

What programs and services do we deliver?
What problems or challenges are we trying to solve?
What value do we deliver to Stakeholders?
What's in it for our Stakeholders?

RELATIONS

What type of relationship does each of our Customer Segments expect us to establish and maintain with them?
Which ones have we established?
How are they integrated with the rest of our business model?
How costly are they?

Examples

- Community
- Co-creation
- Accountability
- Self-Service
- Direct Action
- Automated

CHANNELS

How do we reach Stakeholders?
How do they want to be reached regarding the delivery of our Social Value Proposition?
How do we provide ongoing communications, support, and awareness?

Examples

- Brick and mortar
- Online
- Mobile
- Purchase Touchpoints

STAKEHOLDERS

Who are our Stakeholders?
For whom are we creating value?
Who helps us create Outcomes or our Social Value Propositions?

Category 1

- Clients
- Constituencies
- Recipients

Category 2

- Volunteers
- Participants
- Collaborative Partnerships
- Advocacy

Category 3

- Customers
- Members

Category 4

- High-End Donors
- Low-End Donors
- Philanthropists

COST STRUCTURE

What does it really cost to run our nonprofit operations?
What costs are inherent in our business model?
Which Key Resources and Activities are the most expensive?
What does it cost to run and maintain the Operations Level?

Examples

- Operational Expenditures
- Administrative Costs
- Overhead
- Capital Expenditures
- Fixed Costs
- Variable Costs
- Economies of Scale/Scope

VALUE CAPTURE

What value are Stakeholders truly willing to return or contribute?
What routines and processes do they prefer?
Mission-related milestones?

Financial Measures:

- Donations
- Grants
- Sales Proceeds
- One-time Transactions
- Recurring Transactions
- Other Revenue

Non-Financial Measures:

- Behavior Change
- Social Impact
- Mission-related Milestones/Outcomes
- Membership Sign-ups
- Other metrics and KPIs
- Traffic
- Visitors

INTENDED IMPACT

The Business Model Canvas is a strategic management tool and a planning template, developed by Alexander Osterwalder and widely used by organizations designing their business models and operations. It is a hands-on tool with nine "building blocks" (Key Partners, Key Activities and Key Resources, Value Propositions, Customer Relationships, Channels (to deliver value propositions to targeted customers) and Customer Segments, Cost Structure and Revenue Streams) that could be used in strategic planning sessions as a part of group work to visualize the connections between different elements to form a cohesive business model.

The Nonprofit version of the Business Model Canvas includes Operations and Engagement planning categories and modifies some building blocks - expanding to a 'Social Value Proposition'; replacing 'Customer Relationships' with 'Relations', 'Customer Segments' with 'Stakeholders' and 'Revenue Streams' with 'Value capture'. It's displayed here with two more fields added from the Impact Business Model Canvas - Mission statement and Intended impact.

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This printable version of the canvas can be used for self-reflection and hands-on group activities. Learn more: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14621236>

An interactive template is available at <https://tinyurl.com/5eadv5uk> Scan the QR code to access it.

This template is adapted from the Nonprofit Business Model Canvas (<https://tinyurl.com/4wexxnuy>), based on the Business Model Canvas (<https://tinyurl.com/53vhtcze>) by Business Model Generation and Strategyzer and inspired by the Impact Business Model Canvas (IBMC) (<https://www.impactbusinessmodelcanvas.com/>) It is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International Licence (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>).

